

Assessing uncertainties from reflected irradiance in bifacial PV simulations through a 3D view factor model and rear sensor measurements

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ABSTRACT: Emerging PV applications such as agrivoltaics (agriPV) or bifacial PV present design particularities and are sensitive to irregular surroundings. Realistic and accurate modeling of these applications is both essential to minimize the perceived risk for their financing but is also challenging and requires a very careful model definition and calibration. In this study, we describe a simulation method based on 3D view factors. Using on site measurements, we show how details can influence the irradiance estimation of reference cells on the backside of the same PV module array. Intermediate simulation results such as the evolution of shading over time can provide a first insight of the differences in reflected irradiance measurements. Similarly, we present how the view factors can help to understand the impact of obstacles. Finally, we validate preliminary results of optical simulations by comparing them to on-site measurements.

Keywords: PV modelling, energy yield simulations, bifacial PV, view factors, reflected irradiance.

1. SCIENTIFIC RELEVANCE AND AIM

1.1 Context – State of play

Today's commercial solutions for photovoltaic (PV) energy yield simulations are widely used for modelling standard PV systems. Yet, due to their "black-box" nature, such modelling tools present considerable limitations in addressing design- and technology-specific parameters of PV modules and systems [1,2]. On the other hand, PV systems based on recent and emerging PV technologies, notably bifacial PV, require tailored modelling/simulation approaches (and better understanding) to ensure highly accurate, realistic and reliable assessments of their PV energy yield. In turn, from a grid penetration and investment perspective, realistic and accurate PV energy simulations are essential to minimize the perceived technical (and economic) risk of bifacial PV projects and their financing. Indeed, with the increasing market uptake and deployment of bifacial PV systems, consequent research efforts have been focusing on developing physics-based "customized" models for simulating and assessing the PV energy yield, under bifacial PV-specific conditions (e.g. albedo dependence, rear-side illumination and mismatches, etc).

On the latter, Chudinow et al. [3] introduced a bifacial PV model, with which they investigated and quantified experimentally the influence of ground size, cast ground shadows as well as ground reflectivity on the energy yield of bifacial PV system. Sensitivity analysis-based results of their model, showed that the extension of ground area, which contributes to ground-reflected irradiation, resulted in a slight, asymptotical increase of the energy yield. With the same model, it was possible to show, through ground shadow-free simulations, that the presence of ground shadows can reduce the annual bifacial PV yield by almost 4%, while the influence (and contribution) of ground reflectivity on the energy yield was modelled and validated for five different ground surfaces (dry asphalt, grass, dry grassland, white gravel and white membrane). Đurković et al. in [4] presented a model for more accurate calculation of irradiation for large bifacial PV power plants, i.e. PV power plants characterized by significantly

bigger lengths than heights of PV rows. The model is claimed convenient for hourly meteorological data, which enables calculations of typical daily and annual electricity production of PV power plants. Unlike other existing similar models, the model proposed in [4] considered the fact that less diffuse irradiation incident onto the surface between PV rows which are in the shade of previous PV rows, than entire horizontal diffuse irradiation; thus view factors (VFs) are calculated by simple algebraic relations instead of solving of a double integral. Similarly, Ledesma et al. also developed in 2019 and presented in [5] their VF based two-dimensional model for calculating the rear irradiance in large bifacial PV plants has been developed now, then integrated in SISIFO (an free simulation tool developed at IES-UPM) for static structures and also for horizontal single-axis trackers. In either modelling approaches above, uncertainties (errors) in corresponding energy yield estimation derive primarily from the intrinsic non-uniformities of rear-side irradiance. Finally, in an effort focusing on modelling bifacial PV systems with single-axis tracking, Pelaez et al. [6] evolved the Radiance bifacial PV model [7], including additional modelling steps, i.e. for calculating the array tilt, ground clearance, and row-to-row spacing for each time step. Unlike to the conventional fixed-tilt simulation workflow (annual average bifacial gain calculation based on a single annual sky source), for or a tracked system, multiple scene geometries were considered (for each tracker tilt in 5° increments), along with the solar resource (cumulative hourly values) corresponding to each tracker tilt angle.

1.2 Motivation and aim

The deployment of PV installations, especially in urban, peri-urban and agricultural areas, faces the inevitable constraint of limited space, as available land is (or becomes) scarce in such areas, or has to be shared with other sectors (e.g. agriculture, infrastructure, buildings). Emerging PV applications and configurations, notably agrivoltaics (agriPV), building-integrated PV (BIPV), floating PV and vertical bifacial PV, offer a solution to such constraint, promoting a more rational use of available land or spaces for an optimal so-called landscape integration of PV. However, these new PV applications present design particularities and complex layouts, which

render their modeling and simulation of their energy yield a challenging task, in the same sense as discussed in Section 1.1. PV systems in shared spaces, with complex or irregular surroundings and layouts, require therefore a very careful model definition, yield simulation and comparative assessment with on-site measurements.

An example of how details can influence a measurement of irradiance data (and consequently a PV energy yield simulation) is illustrated in Fig. 1; where we show (on left) the rear side of the first row of monitored PV arrays installed at INES test site, and (on right) the irradiance (W/m^2) data readings, with a 5-minute time step, during an indicative (random) day in winter. The irradiance sensors, i.e. six reference cells denoted A to F from the front to the background respectively are mounted at the same height and with the same tilt angle (30°) as the modules plane and are oriented to the ground. We can see that six sensors on the very same row of modules that (seem to) measure the same data (irradiance in this case), with the same inclination can give significantly different results.

Fig. 1: Observed deviations of in-plane irradiance readings from six identical sensors (reference cells) at the same tilt and orientation (right figure), installed on the rear side of PV modules, monitored at INES test facilities (left figure).

The objectives of this research work is to be able to explain and reproduce these differences by modeling. The modeling tools being sometimes complex, they require more advanced validation and calibration which is sometimes difficult with a limited number of sensors. By understanding the main contribution of irradiance, the model can be fine-tuned for increased accuracy, especially for complex modeling scenes and PV sites-scenarios.

2. APPROACH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modeling aspects

The simulation tool developed for this study is based on TriFactors, a simulation software developed by CEA to model bifacial PV plants. This new version, also based on 3D view factors, allows removing some limitations on the definition of the scene such as taking into account obstacles or structures. The simulation method is globally similar and have the following main steps:

- Define the 3D scene (module, structure, obstacle) with a meshing of the ground
- Estimate the view factors between every elements of the scene.
- For each time step:
 1. Compute the complex shadow of the 3D scene
 2. Transpose global/diffuse irradiance to the surfaces of interest
 3. Combine the contributions of irradiance (direct, diffuse and reflected) to obtain the global irradiance

To simulate the reflected irradiance, the two main approaches are the Ray-Tracing (RT) and the View Factors (VFs). RT is generally very accurate but have a high computation cost. In this abstract, we consider the VFs approaches for his ability of giving contextual information that can help to understand the contribution of irradiance. An important hypothesis of VFs is that it assumes the surface to be Lambertian, i.e. to reflected the light equally in every direction. This hypothesis might not be realistic in all type of ground especially when the sun is low in the horizon. The ideal way to take into account the direction of reflection is to design the BRDF (Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function). However, these functions are difficult to estimate especially with a limited number of sensors available and are not considered in this study.

The reflected irradiance on a surface of interest is computed by summing the contribution of all surfaces as follows:

$$I_{reflected}^i = \frac{1}{A_i} \sum_k^{all\ surface} VF_{k \rightarrow i} * Albedo_k * A_k I^k$$

where I^k is the irradiances received by the surface k (ground or object) including the impact of shadowing, the $Albedo_k$ corresponds to the proportion of light that is reflected, and the view factor $VF_{k \rightarrow i}$ is the proportion of this reflected light reaching the surface of interest. All the view factors are estimated by numerical integration. The contribution through multiple reflection are neglected.

2.2 Data aspects

The input data needed for the model are first the Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), the outside temperature and a general representation of the PV plant. To increase the accuracy, we also have collected with sensors additional information such as the albedo and the Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI). For validation, the site has been equipped by irradiance sensors (cell ref) with the same tilt than the module on both the rear and the front side.

3. SIMULATION RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Understanding sensors difference through modeling

As we have shown in the example of Figure 1, we are assessing a bifacial PV array installed at INES field testing platform, for which we witness significant deviations between the readings from rear-side irradiance sensors, for the same row of PV modules. In this Section, we try to understand and discuss these observations. We also use a modelling approach to give an additional insight into the source of such deviations and their (potential) contribution in uncertainties in PV energy yield simulations/assessments.

A first observation is that the reference cell F gives irradiance readings relatively lower first during a short period in the morning; and then significantly higher compared to all the rest of reference cells. A most plausible explanation is the presence of transient shading on this row, i.e. during a short period in the morning, due to presence of a building in proximity (Fig. 2). In turn, the shading decreases the irradiance incident on the surrounding ground and therefore the light (irradiance) reflected to the sensor in question.

Fig. 2: Simulated shading (left) and photos after the shading moved (right)

To validate the ground the shading, data from camera on INES bench sites are used for a given time comparison. The Figure 3 illustrates a comparison between simulation (top) and image from camera (bottom), for the same time (10:27) and day (May, 11th 2023), on the East of the PV row, near the sensors cell E and F.

We can noticed that some gaps between the PV modules along the mounting structure allow more light incident to (and reflected from) the ground behind the rest of the modules in the same row, which explains higher rear-side irradiance values recorded by the corresponding sensors.

Besides, the fact that this sensor positioned at the side of the row closest to the east, explains its significantly higher irradiance readings in the morning, compared to the afternoon, as the shading of the modules spreads towards west in the morning.

Fig. 3: Comparison of ground shadow near the cell E and F from simulation (top) and camera image (bottom)

Another interesting observation is that the overall irradiance readings measured by the reference cell C are lower than for the rest of the reference cells. Near this sensor, we can notice that there is a combiner box (also present near the other sensors), but also a small structure on the ground, with a metal drain cover. Through View Factor (VF) modelling, we can describe which portion that such obstacles represent in sight of the reference cell (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Understanding the impact of small obstacle using view factors computation.

We can see that the calculated VF of the reference cell to the drain cover is equal to 15.8% which implies a strong

influence of this structure to the overall modelled irradiance – and, consequently, to the resulting (simulated) bifacial PV energy yield. On the other hand, the modelled VF from the cell to the adjacent combiner box is equal to 4.2%. As all the sensors have a box at proximity, we can fairly assume that the monitored irradiance data to be slightly underestimated for all sensors. The VF of the obstacle is not directly equivalent to a loss in irradiance but only represents the portion of an obstacle in the sight of the reference cell. However, this could give a rough idea of the obstacle's impact on the irradiance. Eventually, this type of analysis can be replicated and upscaled at a PV string(s) level, for instance, to understand the impact of the overall structure.

3.2 Preliminary findings in simulations and comparative analysis

In this section, we present results from a comparative analysis between the on-site measurements (monitored) data and the simulations. An essential point to validate is the optical modelling results, especially for the rear-side of the modules, as these may be influenced by considerable inhomogeneities of the incident and reflected irradiance, as discussed in the previous section. Fig. 5 gives an overview of the measured and simulated rear-side irradiance, for the studied bifacial PV array, indicatively for the reference cells B, C and F.

Fig. 5: Comparison of rear irradiance measurement and simulation with a 15mn time step. The reference cells are located in the same array of bifacial module as described in Fig. 1.

We observe that the simulated irradiance for the sensor F is lower than for the two others (B and C), between 8:00 and 8:30, in the morning. This effect has been already observed in the (real) on-site measurements and – as discussed in the previous section, it is explained by the transient near-shading from buildings in proximity, that reduced the amount of light incident to and reflected from the surrounding ground. Yet, this effect is generally underestimated by the model, when compared to the actual measurement. Similarly, the higher simulated irradiance for the sensor F is in agreement with the conclusions also discussed in the previous section: gaps (missing modules) in the mounting structure of the PV array allow more incident and reflected light to the ground below and eventually to the corresponding reference cell. We also observe that the simulated irradiance for the cell C is lower than the other cells as it was expected due to the presence of the drain blocking a part of the ground reflection.

We can notice that there is still some important difference between the measurement and the model that can partially be explained by a lack of calibration of the model. Indeed, the complexity of the model required numerous parameters

that are not necessarily known. More effort will be invested in calibration in ongoing and near-future work, which will also include the results from our comparison between simulated and monitored (actual) bifacial PV power outputs. Other possibilities to explain these differences could be spectral effect or bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) that are not included yet in the tool.

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